

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

Applicability of Historical Laminate Strength Data for Predicting Knockdowns for Wrinkles in Complex Parts

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Overview

- Background
- Wrinkles:
 - In the Literature
 - In the Wild
- Model Set-up
- Results
- Conclusions Future Work

Background

- Increased popularity of:
 - Digital Twins (DT) based on advanced simulations
 - Big Data (BD) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques
 - Automated manufacturing and process control
- All reliant on historical data:
 - For validation/tuning
 - To steer implementation
 - Provide initial conditions
- **But is it valid?**

Background: CerTest

- Reduce development times by:
 - Reducing lower level coupon and detail level test using Big Data
 - Reducing full structure tests using Digital Twins.

Wrinkles: In the Literature

- The data shows:
 - Mechanisms of formation
 - Influence on defect “severity” of:
 - Part Geometry
 - Material Properties
 - Process Parameters
 - Influence of defect on performance
- Studies generally limited to:
 - Induced wrinkles
 - Simply sinusoidal wrinkles
 - Limited repeats
 - Largely simulated

Wrinkles: In the Literature

- Standard characterisation is limited to:
 - Amplitude, A .
 - Wavelength, $2 * l$.
 - Aspect Ratio, $A / (2 * l)$.
 - Wavelength, θ .

- Previous work has identified the need for asymmetric metric.

Wrinkles: In the Literature

- Experimental data available shows large spread with limited meta data.

- [1] Ju, X., et al. (2022).
- [2] Sitohang, R., et al. (2021).
- [3] Bloom, L. D., et al. (2013).
- [4] Mukhopadhyay, S., et al. (2015).
- [5] Mukhopadhyay, S., et al. (2015).

Wrinkles: In the Wild

- Realistic wrinkles can be:
 - Irregular
 - Asymmetric
 - Combined with:
 - Voids
 - In-plane waviness
 - Gaps

Model Set-up

- Inspired by real NCF wrinkles [6]:
 - Single vs. Split Wrinkle.
 - Embedded vs. Visible Wrinkle.
 - Filled vs. Gap underneath.
 - **Constant max angle of 12.5°**
- Using Representative Volume Elements (RVE) :
 - 32 plies (QI and CP).
 - 11mm by 11mm footprint.
 - Custom material models [7].

Results (1)

Results (2)

- [1] Ju, X., et al. (2022).
- [2] Sitohang, R., et al. (2021).
- [3] Bloom, L. D., et al. (2013).
- [4] Mukhopadhyay, S., et al. (2015).
- [5] Mukhopadhyay, S., et al. (2015).

Results (3)

- Characterisation of wrinkles needs enhancement:

Conclusions and Future Work

- The results show:
 - Historical data is poorly characterised leading to large variability.
 - Enhancing wrinkle characterisation to include: maximum angle, asymmetry, *embedded vs. visible (e.g. decay factor)*.
 - Cross-ply strength knockdown roughly 0%-20% lower than Quasi-isotropic.
 - Can generally ignore gaps below wrinkle.
- Future work include:
 - Experimental trials for validation.
 - Continue expanding wrinkle metric space.

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Thank you for listening

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Remaining CerTest Talks

Second-Order Homogenisation of 3D Woven Composites Using Shell Elements
Ms. Athira Anil Kumar, *Thursday, August 3, 13:05 - 13:10, Meeting Room 2B*

Evaluation of Asymmetric Wrinkles Using High Frequency Eddy Current and Ultrasonic Non-Destructive Testing Techniques

Dr. Qiuji Yi, *Thursday, August 3, 15:00 - 15:20, Bar 2*

Use of Micro-CT to Study the Effect of Voiding and Fibre Misalignment on Kink-Band Formation

Mr. Jiraphant Srisuriyachot, *Friday, August 4, 10:20 - 10:40, Meeting Room 2B*

Identification of Subsurface Damage in Multidirectional Composite Laminates Using Full Field Imaging

Mr. Rafael Ruiz Iglesias, *Wednesday, August 2, 12:10 - 12:30, Main Auditorium*

Evaluation of Subsurface Damage on Structural Scale with Integrated Full Field Approaches

Dr. Geir Olafsson, *Thursday, August 3, 10:20 - 10:40, Main Auditorium*

Failure Characterisation of Adhesively Bonded Composite Joints Using a Modified Arcan Fixture

Mr. David Brearley, *Thursday, August 3, 10:20 - 10:40, Hall 1A*

Identifying Damage in Multidirectional GFRP Composite Laminates Using Thermoelastic Stress Analysis

Prof. Janice Barton, *Thursday, August 3, 12:50 - 13:10, Hall 1A*

Bayesian Calibration of a Finite Element C-Spar Model Using Digital Image Correlation

Dr. Carl Scarth, *Wednesday, August 2, 10:40 - 11:00, Hall 1A*

References:

- [1] Ju, X., Xiao, J., Wang, D., Zhao, C., Gao, T., & Wang, X. (2022). Effect of gaps/overlaps induced waviness on the mechanical properties of automated fiber placement (AFP)-manufactured composite laminate. *Materials Research Express*.
- [2] Sitohang, R. D. R., Groupe, W. J. B., Warnet, L. L., & Akkerman, R. (2021). Effect of in-plane fiber waviness defects on the compressive properties of quasi-isotropic thermoplastic composites. *Composite Structures*.
- [3] Bloom, L. D., Wang, J., & Potter, K. D. (2013). Damage progression and defect sensitivity: An experimental study of representative wrinkles in tension. *Composites Part B: Engineering*.
- [4] Mukhopadhyay, S., Jones, M. I., & Hallett, S. R. (2015). Tensile failure of laminates containing an embedded wrinkle; numerical and experimental study. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*.
- [5] Mukhopadhyay, S., Jones, M. I., & Hallett, S. R. (2015). Compressive failure of laminates containing an embedded wrinkle; Experimental and numerical study. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*.
- [6] Martin, C. J., Smith, R., Mavrogordato, M., Rosini, S., Maes, V., Sinclair, I., McMahon, T., & Kratz, J. (2022). Time resolved in-situ CT scanning of non-crimp fabric forming. In Proceedings of the 20th European Conference on Composite Materials, Vol. 2, pp 1052-1059.
- [7] El Said, B., and Hallett, S. R. (2018). Multiscale Surrogate Modelling of the Elastic Response of Thick Composite Structures with Embedded Defects and Features. *Composite Structures*.